

ABOUT THE ANALYSIS OF SHAROF RASHIDOV'S ACTIVITIES IN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

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Annotation: This scientific article provides a comprehensive analysis of the activities of the author Sharof Rashidov in international relations, examining his contribution to the foreign policy of the Soviet Union and independent Uzbekistan, his influence on the development of international relations, economic cooperation and diplomatic relations. Sharof Rashidov's political approaches aimed at strengthening relations with the countries of Central Asia and developing countries, as well as his role in the socialist bloc, and his role in increasing the prestige of Uzbekistan in the international arena are also analyzed. The author analyzes Sharof Rashidov's successes in foreign policy, what significance he had for Uzbekistan and how he helped shape the country's position in the global arena as an independent state.

Keywords: Sharof Rashidov, Uzbek SSR, international relations, foreign policy, economic cooperation, cultural ties, diplomatic relations.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur ilmiy maqolada muallif Sharof Rashidovning xalqaro munosabatlardagi faoliyati har tomonlama tahlil qilinib, uning Sovet Ittifoqi va mustaqil O'zbekistonning tashqi siyosatiga qo'shgan hissasi, xalqaro munosabatlar, iqtisodiy hamkorlik va diplomatik munosabatlar rivojiga ta'siri o'rganiladi. Sharof Rashidovning Markaziy Osiyo davlatlari va rivojlanayotgan davlatlar bilan munosabatlarni mustahkamlashga qaratilgan siyosiy yondashuvlari, sotsialistik ittifoqdagi o'рни, O'zbekistonning xalqaro maydondagi nufuzini oshirishdagi roli ham tahlil qilinadi. Muallif Sharof Rashidovning tashqi siyosatdagi muvaffaqiyatlari, uning O'zbekiston uchun qanday ahamiyati borligi, mustaqil davlat sifatida jahon maydonidagi mavqeini shakllantirishga qanday hissa qo'shganini tahlil qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Sharof Rashidov, O'zbekiston SSR, xalqaro munosabatlar, tashqi siyosat, iqtisodiy hamkorlik, madaniy aloqalar, diplomatik munosabatlar.

Аннотация: В данной научной статье дается комплексный анализ деятельности автора Шарофа Рашидова в международных отношениях, рассматривается его вклад во внешнюю политику Советского Союза и независимого Узбекистана, его влияние на развитие международных отношений, экономического сотрудничества и дипломатических отношений. Также анализируются политические подходы Шарофа Рашидова, направленные на укрепление отношений со странами Центральной Азии и развивающимися странами, а также его роль в социалистическом блоке, и его роль в повышении престижа Узбекистана на международной арене. Автор анализирует успехи Шарофа Рашидова во внешней политике, какое значение он имел для Узбекистана и как он помог сформировать положение страны на мировой арене как независимого государства.

Ключевые слова: Шароф Рашидов, Узбекская ССР, международные отношения, внешняя политика, экономическое сотрудничество, культурные связи, дипломатические отношения.

Introduction

Sharof Rashidov made a significant contribution to the establishment of independent Uzbekistan. He is considered one of the key political figures who left a noticeable mark on both domestic and foreign policy of the country. Rashidov's scientific works in the field of international relations were relevant not only during the Soviet period, but also after Uzbekistan gained independence. This article is devoted to the analysis of

the role of Sharof Rashidov in the field of international relations, his activities on the diplomatic front and the significance of this activity for the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Sharof Rashidov served as the head of the Uzbek Soviet Socialist Republic from 1959 to 1983[1]. His policies were characterized by an effort to defend the specific needs and interests of Uzbekistan within the unified system of the Soviet Union, while simultaneously promoting them at the regional level in Central Asia.

During the Soviet period, the leaders of the republics played a key role in determining social, economic, and political policies in their territories. Sharof Rashidov, as the head of the Uzbek SSR, also attempted to actively influence the country's foreign policy.

During the Soviet Union, Sharof Rashidov prioritized the development of multilateral cooperation with Central Asian countries in the field of international relations and diplomacy.

He linked Uzbekistan's success in the agricultural sector and industry with opportunities to enter the world market, considering it necessary to provide economic support to other republics of the USSR. In particular, Sharof Rashidov attached great importance to the role of Uzbekistan in cotton production and the economic significance of its exports. The export of Uzbek cotton, along with other strategic goods, to Central Asia and other former Soviet republics played an important role in his foreign policy doctrine[2].

Problem statement

Key strategies and priorities that determine foreign policy:

✓ During the development of economic relations, intensive trade exchange took place between the Republic of Uzbekistan and other republics of the Soviet Union.

✓ During his activity, Sharof Rashidov paid significant attention to strengthening cultural ties, which had a positive impact on the development of the cultural and scientific potential of Uzbekistan within the Soviet Union.

The foreign policy course pursued by Sharof Rashidov played a significant role in the system of Soviet foreign policy.

Its main objective was to expand the opportunities of the Uzbek SSR in the world economic market and strengthen its position in the international community. For this reason, Sharof Rashidov paid special attention to the development of interaction with states in the development stage.

Research methods

In the course of studying and analyzing this article was used a set of historical research methods. Among them, both general scientific approaches such as analysis, synthesis, generalization and comparison, and specific methods based on hypotheses and analogies were used deduction and induction.

It is important to note that special methods are tools adapted to the specific requirements and tasks of a particular discipline. Such methods in historical science include, in particular, the chronological and historical-comparative approaches.

Results and examples

Rashidov's foreign policy successes were largely due to his policy of economic growth and development of trade relations. He actively sought to establish economic relations with countries such as India, Egypt, China and other states developing at the same stage.

This cooperation opened up new opportunities for Uzbekistan in the field of exchange of advanced technologies and experience, which had a beneficial effect on the development of agriculture, industry and energy. As an example, we can cite the strengthening of cooperation with India in the agricultural sector and the development of industrial and transport links with China[3].

Sharof Rashidov's foreign policy was characterized by the desire to establish equal relations with both the states that were part of the Soviet Union and other independent countries. At the same time, he paid special attention to the specific economic needs of Uzbekistan. His political doctrine was oriented toward the development of mutually beneficial cooperation between states.

An important part of Sharof Rashidov's foreign policy is a strategy aimed at strengthening international cooperation. He actively developed diplomatic and economic ties both within the Soviet Union and with foreign countries, which allowed Uzbekistan to expand its international relations. These measures contributed to the growth of Uzbekistan's authority in the global economic arena and the influx of foreign trade and investment resources.

During the foreign policy activities of Sharof Rashidov, emphasis was placed not only on the development of economic relations, but also on strengthening cultural and scientific ties. His strategic goal was closer integration of Uzbekistan into the international scientific and cultural community.

To achieve this goal, special attention was paid to the participation of Uzbekistan in various international conferences, symposiums and other events, as well as the active popularization of Uzbek culture abroad. At the same time, he paid significant attention to expanding international cooperation in the field of education and science of the Republic of Uzbekistan[4].

Sharof Rashidov played a significant role in the formation of the foreign policy strategy of the socialist bloc.

Despite the entry of the Uzbek SSR into the Soviet Union, Sh.Rashidov actively contributed to the development of mutually beneficial economic and political ties with the countries of Central Asia and other former Soviet republics. He paid special attention to strengthening trade and economic relations, in particular, between Russia and Ukraine[5].

Writer Sh.Rashidov paid considerable attention to the development of science, education and culture in the republic. With his participation, Tashkent turned into one of the cultural centers of Asia. An important event in the cultural life of the republic was the VII Conference of Writers of Asian and African Countries, held in Tashkent in September 1983. The conference was attended by 129 delegates and guests from 70 countries of Asia, Africa, America and Europe, as well as representatives of a number of other states. Representatives of international organizations took part in the work of the conference[6].

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Sharof Rashidov's contribution to international relations had a significant impact on the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. His diplomatic strategy allowed him not only to secure Uzbekistan's significant status within the USSR, but also to play an important role in shaping the foreign policy of the independent state.

Rashidov's achievements in international cooperation, particularly in the economic sphere, contributed to strengthening Uzbekistan's position on the world stage.

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